

COMPOSITION AND STRUCTURE OF FIBROIN ISOLATED FROM SILKWORM COCOONS

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Bombyx mori is considered a silk fibroin, and it consists of a central core of the silk fiber and is surrounded by a layer of sericin. The composition of silk fiber consists of fibroin (72-81%), sericin (19-28%) and waxes. Fibroin acts as a matrix of silk fibers and provides mechanical strength. According to the chemical composition, Bombyx moritola consists of at least 16 amino acid residues, and their ratio differs between different regions of the fibroin supramolecular structure. Generalization of glycine, alanine, and serine residues 90% is organized; their sequence is expressed by the general formula. Fig. 1 shows the projections of segments of macromolecules forming a - spiral and b - layered structures. α - the hydrogen bonds in the spiral structure of the molecule are formed, and the hydrophobic fragments move to the periphery. b - In the folded structure, macromolecules are arranged parallel or antiparallel, forming a layer or layer (b-sheet).

Although sericin is a protein in structure, unlike fibroin, it causes allergies in the body and has side effects. Therefore, fibroin requires purification from sericin before it can be used for medical purposes. Silk has a high molecular weight (200-350 kDa or more), large repeating modular hydrophobic domains interrupted by small hydrophilic groups.. Silk fibroin, like creatine and collagen, belongs to fibrillar proteins. The structural elements of silk fibers are macrofibrils with a width of up to 105 nm, which in turn consist of spirally wound nanofibrils with a diameter of 90-170 nm.. Nanofibrils play an important role in increasing the strength of silk. The length of the fibroin macrochain is 150 nm; macrochain diameter 0.45 nm. Silk fibers are mainly composed of two proteins, sericin and fibroin; they also contain small amounts of other amino acid residues and various impurities: oils, waxes, and mineral salts. Depending on the type of cocoon, fibroin is 66.5-73.5, sricin is 26.5-33.5 m.%.

Bombyx mori silk fibroin consists of heavy (H) and light (L) chains (H – and L – fibroin, respectively) connected by disulfide bonds. In addition, silk contains a 25 kDa glycoprotein called P-25. , there is a glycoprotein, which is also attached to these chains without a covalent bond. Hydrophobic domains of heavy chains contain amino acid repetitions (Ala, Ser, Tyr, Val) and can form antiparallel β -layers (β -layer structure The L chain is hydrophilic and relatively elastic in nature.

P-25 protein plays an important role in maintaining the integrity of the silk complex.

P-25 protein plays an important role in maintaining the integrity of the silk complex. H-fibroin, L-fibroin and P-25 are found in silk in a ratio of 6:6:1. Purified and processed silk is purified from light L-chain, P-25 glycoprotein. Instead, it contains heavy chain homodimers with a molecular weight of ~330 kDa, they are formed by separate proteins (~160 kDa). Hydrophobic domains of silk polymer chains, consisting of repeated amino acid sequences, are attached to nanocrystals. (b - floors) were collected. Hydrophilic bonds between these hydrophobic domains consist of large and polar side chains that form the amorphous part of the protein's secondary structure..

Chemically, Bombyx moritola consists of at least 16 amino acid residues, the ratio of which varies between different regions of the fibroin supramolecular structure.. (Table 1). The total mole fraction of glycerol, alanine, serine and tyrosine residues is 90%; their sequence is represented by the general formula bn. Silk is a fiber structure after silkworm spinning, which is basically an anti-parallel β -layerThe physical and mechanical properties of regenerated silk fibroin depend on the conformation of the molecular chain and crystal structure. Figure 1 shows projections of segments of macromolecules forming a-helix and b-sheet structures. α -helical structure is formed by hydrogen bonds inside the molecule, and hydrophobic fragments move to the periphery moves. In the β -folded structure, macromolecules are arranged parallel or antiparallel, forming a folded layer or layer (β -sheet).1-jadval

Amio acid composition of Bombyx mori silk fibroin

Amino acid	Content, mol.%		
	General	H-fibroin	L-fibroin
Glycerin	42,9	49,4	10,0
Alanine	30,0	29,8	16,9
cool	12,2	11,3	7,9
Tyrosine	4,8	4,6	3,4

Valin	2,5	2,0	7,4
Aspartic acid	1,9	0,65	15,4
Glutamic acid	1,4	0,70	8,4
Threonine	0,92	0,45	2,8
phenylalanine	0,67	0,39	2,7
Methionine	0,37	-	0,37
Isolation	0,64	0,14	7,3
license	0,55	0,09	7,2
proline	0,45	0,31	3,0
arginine	0,51	0,18	3,8
histidine	0,19	0,09	1,6
lysine	lysine	lysine	lysine

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